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Wearable textile-based sensor for sweat sodium chloride monitoring applications

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ABSTRACT

Continuous monitoring of physiological analytes like sweat is extremely beneficial in fields such as healthcare and physical fitness. Commercially available physiological monitors have good working quality, but they are unpleasant and cumbersome. Here, we proposed a textile-based flexible, low-cost, easy-to-manufacture impedimetric sensor based on layered assembly for sweat monitoring applications. This proof-of-concept model explores the changes in the impedance of textile sensors due to variations in quantity and concentrations of saline concentrations. Initially, the textile capacitive sensor was fabricated by sandwiching a textile between perforated copper electrodes. The surface property of the selected fabric was characterized using standard SEM and drop shape analyzer. Later, the performance of fabricated sensor was evaluated using an impedance analyzer for different concentrations of saline in the range of 0.3–0.9% and at certain intervals for 1 h. Permeable structure and high wettability (water contact angle $\sim 25^\circ$) of selected textile fabric indicated its high suitability for sweat sensing. For the given geometry of developed sensors, 900 μl of saline solution and 60 min drying time at 37°C , were the optimum volume for completely wetting and the duration for completely drying the textile sensor, respectively. In addition, the impedance variation was linear ($R^2 \sim 0.862$), and the sensor showed good reproducibility. Its sensitivity and limit of detection were 128.6 $\Omega/\%$ saline concentrations and 0.334% saline concentration, respectively. The fabricated sensor demonstrated similar device behavior in both laboratory and real-time testing. We believe that the proposed textile-based sensor is highly suitable for future non-invasive health monitoring applications.

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Textile sensor; saline; sweat; sodium chloride; impedimetric sensor; health monitoring

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

1. Introduction

Technological advancement in the biomedical field has significantly contributed to improvements in human health. Biosensing technology is playing a vital role in monitoring

human health. Body fluids are full of enriched information to analyze human health and daily physiology (Abellán-Llobregat et al., 2017; Anastasova et al., 2017; Bandodkar et al., 2019; Choi et al., 2019; Glennon et al., 2016; Zafar et al., 2022). The level of sodium chloride in sweat is highly

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helpful in identifying the electrolyte imbalance that may cause conditions such as muscle cramps, dehydration, or even hyponatremia (Epstein & Moran, 2019; Maughan & Shirreffs, 2019; Veniamakis et al., 2022). Understanding the sodium chloride level of the human body is very crucial not only for athletes during their regular training or competitions but also for individuals, especially during hot weather (Amawi et al., 2023; Scherrer & Daanen, 2021). The World Health Organization (WHO) has standardized the recommended dietary salt intake of around 5 g per day and those who have the risk of heart disease are better to consume less than 2 g of sodium per day. Monitoring NaCl concentrations is essential for understanding salt contamination levels and potential damage risks (Jit et al., 2022).

Various sensors are found to be very effective in detecting human perspiration with and without physical contact (He et al., 2019; Kumar et al., 2024; Kumar et al., 2019; Mavelil et al., 2024; Tabasum et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2021; Zhai et al., 2020). For example, Kumar *et al.* (Kumar et al., 2022) developed a screen-printed, silver-manganese nanocomposite-based electrochemical sensor to detect chloride ions in sweat with a detection range from 5 up to 200 mM. Also, Sopstad *et al.* (2020) designed a stamp-sized, flexible, wireless electrochemical sensor platform for potentiometric pH and amperometric chloride sensing, utilizing graphene oxide and Ag/AgCl electrodes, respectively with high sensitivity and low inter-sensor standard deviation. Similarly, Lei *et al.* (2023) developed a low-cost epidermal microfluidic patch using copper foil tape, that simultaneous monitoring of sweat rate and sweat chloride concentration *via* an admittance pulse-based method. The sensor used double-layer capacitance (two structures: parallel assembly and interdigitated) to calculate total admittance when the sweat advances along the microchannel. In another report, Parrilla *et al.* (2016) reported a wearable potentiometric sensor by combining polyurethane-based ion-selective membranes and inks with a serpentine sensor pattern. The developed stretchable potentiometric sensor was highly effective in detecting the physiological sodium (Na) and potassium (K) levels in sweat before, during, and after prolonged exercise. Wu *et al.* (2023) developed a single strand of fiber that could be woven into textiles for on-body sweat sensing. The fiber consisted of two sensing electrodes modified with sensing materials, such as gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) as well as ion-sensitive membranes (ISMs) for sensing Na⁺ concentrations. Meanwhile, Ag/AgCl-based pseudo reference electrodes (p-REs) were also incorporated into fibers by integrating Ag/AgCl ink. The Na⁺ ion sensitivity was recorded to be 43.1 ± 3.5 mV/decade in the artificial sweat. It is observed that the majority of the aforementioned design approaches are based on electrochemical, interdigitated mechanisms, and printing technology. These design approaches are constrained by tedious fabrication processes, the requirement of additional treatments like oxygen plasma exposure during fabrication, usage of toxic chemicals, discomfort, and little surface area to interact with analytes, restricting the amount of physiological data that is currently obtainable by wearable bioelectronics.

Here, we report a textile-based impedimetric sensor, wherein, the selected textile was used as a sensing layer. Its impedance variation offers the detection of saline solution which serves as a valuable analogue to the sodium chloride content in human sweat. This proof-of-concept design is inspired by the possible use of cost-effective materials, and ease of the fabrication process as well as the option to scale up. The proposed sensor was developed by sandwiching the textile layer between thin perforated copper electrodes and post-treatments. The selected cotton fabric demonstrated wettability with permeable microstructures in its material characterization. The prepared textile-based sensor exhibited similar device behavior during laboratory testing and real-time testing with human sweat.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

Fabric (100% cotton) was purchased from the Sabaev, Turkey, with the thickness of 0.165 mm. For the electrical connections and electrodes, 3MTM Copper Foil EMI Shielding Tape 1181 (3M, St. Paul, Minnesota, USA) was used. This tape is a general-purpose 99.9% pure copper foil tape with an electrically conductive acrylic adhesive. The tape with dimensions of 1 in × 66 ft' and a total thickness of 0.066 ± 0.005 mm, was applied to the cotton fabric layer to make a sandwich structure. The sodium chloride saline (9 g/l or 0.9%) was bought from Hemofarm, Serbia.

2.2. Sensor design and fabrication

The structure of the 3D textile sensor was composed of five layers (three layers of textile fabric and two perforated copper electrodes). The cotton textile was employed in the middle (sensing layer) due to its features such as breathability, hydrophilicity, wearing comfortability, hypoallergenic nature, and biodegradability. These cotton textile samples were prepared in size of 3 × 3 cm. The sensor structure was fabricated by adhering the copper (Cu) tape on both sides of the fabric with an overall thickness of 0.297 mm followed by the mechanical press using a roller in order to employ them as the sensor's electrodes (Figure 1). Before adhering, 9 holes of 2 mm diameter were made on both sides of Cu electrodes using a Graphtec cutter plotter (CE6000-60 Plus, Japan). The holes were made for the insertion of fluid (saline) at one side and the other side is for breathability and helps in drying afterwards. The fabricated textile sensor was embedded (sewn) with another fabric of the same material aiming to simulate the condition when it can be embedded or attached to clothing making an overall thickness of 0.627 mm.

This design of the sensor was aimed at facilitating the rapid absorption and evaporation of bodily fluids when the sensor is attached to the clothing. The five-layer structure was carefully designed to optimize sensor performance and stability. The center separating layer is crucial for moisture diffusion, which was chosen with minimal thickness and

Figure 1. Design of proposed textile-based sensor based on a perforated copper sandwich textile architecture, illustrating its top view, side view, attachment with another fabric (a de-attached pocket in our clothing), and under bending condition.

high absorbency. Two outer layers (outer fabric layers) provide essential electrical isolation and structural support, preventing adhesive degradation and signal interference. Through iterative experimental testing, we determined that five layers offered the optimal balance in moisture diffusion and reduced user comfort. The planned location of the proposed sensor should be in a tiny pocket made from the inside of the clothing we wear while working out or doing laborious tasks. The proposed sensor can be used as an indicator of hydration status, determining if an individual is adequately hydrated or if they need to replenish fluids lost through sweating.

2.3. Characterization, sensing set-up, and sensor's performance evaluation

The surface morphology of the cotton textile material was analyzed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, Hitachi TM3030, Japan, accelerating voltage of 10 kV). The contact angle was measured by a drop shape analyzer system (DSA-25, KRÜSS). For investigating the sensor performance, a sensing setup as shown in Figure S1 (supporting information) is established wherein the textile sensor sample was placed on a hot plate at a fixed temperature of 37 °C. The sensor sample was tested for the concentration range (0.3–0.9%) of saline. In the arrangement, the sample was connected to an impedance analyzer (Hioki IM3590, Japan). The wetting and drying processes were monitored using a thermal camera (TI160, ULIRVISION China). To investigate the wetting saturation and the minimum drying time required to dry the completely wet sample, we performed two studies, namely, volume optimization and time optimization at a stable temperature of 37 °C. For volume optimization, the desired amount of saline volume

(700 μ l–1.2 ml) was dropped on the sensor. Then, we recorded the measured parameters (impedance Z , phase angle θ , capacitance C) for 60 min at intervals of 5 min. In the drying time optimization, the measured parameters were recorded at the interval of 5 min from the wet condition until the completely dry condition. In every optimization, the temperature was recorded using a thermal camera. During the sensing, we prepared eight different concentrations of saline solution in the range of 0.3–0.9% by diluting it with deionized water. The desired amount of the different concentrations of saline was then dropped on the sensor and the parameters were studied similar to the above optimization steps. For proof-of-concept, the sensor behavior was evaluated during the exercise (running on the treadmill) in a closed gym ambient. A headband embedded with a textile sensor was placed on the head of the volunteer. The variation in the impedance and phase angle of this sensor was monitored over time (20 min) using an interfaced impedance analyzer and computer. The volunteer signed the informed consent form. Before measurement, the detailed experimental setup and method were explained to the volunteer.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of textile fabric

For analyzing the surface quality of the selected fabric, the morphology and water contact angle were analyzed using standard SEM and drop shape analyzer as shown in Figure 2. The SEM image shows the woven structure of the textile (Figure 2a). The textile was also found to be high quality, and permeable (due to inter-fiber gaps), favoring for liquid to pass through it. A denser thread count was

Figure 2. (a) SEM image showing woven structure with denser thread counts in the morphology of the selected fabric. (b) The water contact angle of the selected fabric.

Figure 3. Intrinsic behavior of as-fabricated textile-based sensing structure: (a) capacitance—frequency, (b) impedance—frequency, and (c) phase angle—frequency characteristics.

observed on its surface. The threads were found to be of regular shape with almost uniform diameter. Figure 2b illustrates the water contact angle that is required to examine the wettability of the selected fabric. The water contact angle was measured to be $\sim 25^\circ$, confirming the highly hydrophilic fabric (Dutra et al., 2017; Kumar et al., 2022). High wettability and permeability of the fabric also indicate comparatively faster transportation of a liquid within the fabric's area as well as from the fabric to the next layer (capacitor's electrodes) due to capillary force action (Taleb Em, 2013).

3.2. Characterization of textile-based sensing structure

To understand the intrinsic behaviors of the fabricated textile-based sensing structure, we investigated its behavior by examining the variations in its capacitance, impedance, and phase angle with respect to frequency change in drying

conditions (before wetting it with saline) as shown in Figure 3. From the capacitance-frequency characteristic, it was observed that the capacitance values of the fabricated structure decreased gradually with an increase in the frequency. The capacitance values varied from 81.55 to 58.2 pF over the frequency range of 100 Hz–5 kHz. At 1 kHz, the capacitance was measured to be 66.9 pF (Figure 3a). We also noticed that upon increasing the number of textile layers (dielectric) up to three, the capacitance of the fabricated structure was found to be decreased (Table ST1, supporting information). The impedance-frequency characteristic (Figure 3b) revealed that the impedance of the capacitive structure decreased gradually at a lower frequency range of 100–250 Hz. After that, it decreased steadily with a comparatively faster rate as frequency increased from 300 Hz to 5 kHz and exhibited a tendency of stabilizing near a higher frequency range (~ 3 –5 kHz), indicating reduced charge and

discharged time of a capacitor. The impedance of the textile-based sensing structure was measured to be 8.77, 1.54, and 350 k Ω at frequencies 100 Hz, 1, and 5 kHz, respectively. Figure 3c presents the phase angle as a function of frequency for the proposed sensor structure. The phase angle was changed from 75° to 86° over the frequency range and it was found to be very close to the ideal capacitor value ($\sim 90^\circ$), indicating the highly capacitive nature of the fabricated textile-based sensing structure in drying conditions (Manjakkal et al., 2020).

3.3. Wetting and drying analyses of textile sensor (saline volume optimization and drying time optimization of fabric)

3.3.1. Saline volume optimization

The wetting analysis aims to quantify the wetting that occurs within the dielectric layer. For this purpose, a saline solution was used, that serves as an analogue of human sweat's sodium chloride and is commonly available at pharmacies. The volume of saline was optimized to examine the wetting saturation of the fabric (minimum volume of saline required for completely wetting the fabric). Different saline volumes were investigated and the parameters such as capacitance, phase angle, and impedance were measured and compared with measured parameters before the wet

condition, as shown in Figure 4a, 4b, and 4c, respectively. Figure 4a illustrates the capacitance of the sensor for different volumes ranging from 700 μl to 1.2 ml over the frequency range of 100 Hz–5 kHz. The capacitance of the sensor was found to be increased ($\sim 2.47\text{--}5.92\ \mu\text{F}$ at 100 Hz) upon increasing concentrations (from 700–1200 μl) in comparison to its dry condition. This is possibly due to the higher relative permittivity of saline (79) than the fabric (1.6). The presence of higher permittivity material (i.e. saline) allows the capacitive sensor to store more electric charge at a given voltage. The electric field within the capacitor becomes more concentrated in the dielectric, resulting in a higher capacitance. The capacitance of the sensor for every volume of saline was tended to almost constant, at approaching to higher frequency (after 1–5 kHz). The variation in capacitance of the sensor from dry condition (pF) to wet condition (μF) is found in agreement with the previously reported studies (Manjakkal et al., 2020; Martínez-Estrada et al., 2023).

Reverse to the capacitance variation of a fabricated sensor, upon an increase in the volume of saline solution from 700 μl to 1.2 ml, a decrease in the impedance values of the sensor was observed in comparison to its value in the dry condition (Figure 4c). Figure 4b represents the variation in the phase angles upon an increase in the aforementioned volumes of the saline solution. Before the wetting sensor

Figure 4. (a) Capacitance, (b) phase angle, (c) impedance vs. frequency characteristics of the fabricated sensor for different wetting volumes (700 μl –1.2 ml) of saline solution (0.9%). (d) Impedance variation for sensor upon different saline volumes at a frequency of 1 kHz.

Figure 5. (a) Impedance variation of the fabricated sensor over time. (b) Infrared thermal camera images (at intervals of 5 min) indicate different stages of the sensor's drying.

was in the dry condition, the sensor's phase angle was found to be close to 90° , indicating a tendency to be a purely capacitive element. As we started increasing the volumes of saline solution, the phase angles began to shift towards 0° . The phase angles of the sensor for 700, 800, 900 μl , 1, and 1.2 ml were found to be approximately -6.02° , -9.89° , -10.82° , -9.81° and -12.55° , respectively in the lower frequency range (100 Hz – 1 kHz) while the phase angle at different saline volumes started to become almost constant approaching to higher frequency range (1–5 kHz). At a frequency of ~ 1 kHz, the impedance of the fabricated sensor was found to be decreased from 5.79 to 1.24 k Ω as the saline volume increased from 700 to 900 μl and it remained almost constant after 900 μl until 1.2 ml saline volumes (Figure 4d). It was found that the minimum volume of saline required to completely wet the fabric was 900 μl . There were no further significant variations and after 1.2 ml, the sensor was in an overflow state. However, it also depends on the diffusion rate of ions of saline from solution to fabric (equivalent to the secretion rate for human sweat from the skin to attached fabric). From Figure 4d, it can be concluded that the proposed sensor can be efficiently used for volume detection.

We also tested the effect of variation in the number of textile layers (sensing layer) on the capacitance of the textile sensor. We dropped a fixed volume of saline (900 μl) on

the sensors having one to three inner textile sensing layers and measured the capacitance of three sensors at 1 kHz frequency. The sensors' capacitances were found to be decreased by nearly two orders of magnitude (Table ST1, supporting information) upon increasing the number of textile layers from one to three. The decrease in capacitance with increasing thickness of the sensing layer (increasing number of fabric layers) suggests that the sensor has a reduction in the sensing performance, making it less responsive to the variation in ionic concentration of saline. The sensor with a thinner sensing layer (single layer) exhibits a stronger capacitive response, indicating higher sensitivity to saline solution. Increasing the thickness of cotton fabric can also increase the response time due to increased distance for diffusion of the fluid (saline).

3.3.2. Drying time optimization

To identify the diffusion rate, we optimized the time to completely dry the textile sensor which was wet using the desired amount of saline solution. The impedance of the sensor was examined for 1 h by measuring values at the interval of 5 min. It was observed that the cotton fabric sensor took ~ 5 s to absorb the desired amount (1.2 ml) of the saline, and evaporation began approximately 3 min after the diffusion was completed, indicating a completely wet

Figure 6. (a) Impedance variation as a function of frequency, and (b) Nyquist plot showing capacitive behavior (lower frequency range) of textile-based sensors for the saline concentration range of 0.3–0.9%, analyzed using impedance spectroscopy.

condition of the sensor fabric. The impedance of the sensor was found to be increased with an increase in time. This characteristic was found to be approximately linear (Figure 5a). After 60 min, the sensor was observed to be completely dry which was assured by thermal camera imaging (Figure 5b), and at this moment there was a 4-order increment in the impedance of the sensor. The high temperature for instance 37°C of hot plate (equivalent to the normal human body temperature) is enough to increase the kinetic energy of the ions in the saline solution. This increased kinetic energy generally leads to a higher diffusion rate of saline ions resulting in a quicker establishment of a stable charge distribution within the capacitive sensor thereby changing its impedance (Kumar et al., 2022).

3.4. Performance of textile-based sensor

Eight different concentrations of saline solution in a range of 0.3–0.9% were tested on the fabricated textile sensor using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy over a frequency range of 100 Hz – 20 kHz as presented in Figure 6. It was observed that the impedance of the sensor decreased with the increase in the frequency. In the lower frequency range, the fall-off in impedance was faster than that of the higher frequency range. At both 100 Hz and 20 kHz, an approximately 3.5-fold decrease in the impedance of the sensor was found upon an increase in saline concentrations from 0.3 to 0.9%, (Figure 6a).

The Nyquist plot for the textile capacitive sensor is shown in Figure 6b. It was noticed that the impedance of the sensor in the imaginary part of the complex impedance (that represents the vertical axis) increased with a decrease in the frequency for all saline concentrations. This indicates that the fabricated textile-based sensor has more capacitive behavior in the lower frequency range and vice-versa in the higher frequency range. The presence of a straight line in the lower frequency range represents diffusion of saline ions. We found that with the increase in saline concentration from 0.3 to 0.9%, the impedance values in the imaginary part of complex impedance were increased, indicating that the more capacitive at 0.3% saline concentration than that of 0.9% saline concentration. We noticed that there was

Figure 7. Calibration plot between saline concentration and sensor's impedance. Impedance values were taken at 1 kHz frequency.

no semicircle in the higher frequency region for all saline concentrations. The absence of a semicircle in the higher frequency range in the Nyquist plot indicates the high conductivity of the sensor electrode during reaction with saline-coated fabric (Manjakkal et al., 2020; Yuan et al., 2016).

In addition, the variation in the impedance of the textile sensor was found to be linear. The calibration curve between saline concentrations and the measured impedance is shown in Figure 7. The coefficient of correlation (R^2) was extracted from GraphPad Prism10 software upon linear regression fit analysis. R^2 was found to be 0.862, suggesting good sensing behavior of the textile-based sensor. The impedance at 0.3, 0.35, 0.45, 0.55, 0.6, 0.7, 0.85, and 0.9%, saline concentrations were measured to be 166.5, 121.5, 122.4, 121.9, 113.2, 89.7, 76.3, 74.1 Ω , respectively. The impedance was measured after 20 min of dropping the saline solution. Moreover, five replicates of the reference sensor were tested for the aforementioned concentrations of saline. The relative standard deviation and average variations of measured impedance at 1 kHz frequency for all replicates at different concentrations are represented in Figure S2 (supporting information). R^2 was found to be 0.904 for mean impedance values, indicating the reproducibility of the sensor towards the detection of saline concentrations. The sensitivity and limit of detection (LoD) of the proposed

Figure 8. Performance of textile-based sensor in a real application: (a) an image of a volunteer wearing a textile sensor embedded inner side of the headband performing running on a treadmill (left side) and thermal-camera images indicate the measured body temperature of a volunteer during running at different time intervals. (b) Impedance and (c) phase angle variation over the time while running. The insets show the impedance variation during period 600–1200 s and phase angle variation from period 800–1200 s.

textile sensor were found to be 128.6Ω /saline concentration (%) and 0.334 saline concentration (%), respectively.

In this work, we also performed testing of wearable textile sensors in a real-time condition, while it was worn by an informed volunteer walking on a treadmill. The sensor was embedded with a headband (synthetic polar fleece material) at its inner wall facing to forehead of the volunteer (Figure 8a). To record the sensing behavior (under this running trail 1) a computer was interfaced with an impedance analyzer via RS 232 cable (Figure S3, supporting information). The variation in the impedance and the phase angle of the sensor was continuously recorded for 20 min. A thermal camera was used to observe the body temperature (face by red circle in thermal images) at different time intervals as shown in Figure 8a (right side). We evaluated the variations in the impedance as presented in Figure 8b. A very high impedance (13–20 G Ω) was measured from the sensor at no exercise (running) condition as well as in the inception of exercise, indicating its dry state. After 30 s, the impedance was observed to sharply decline to the impedance of $0.58 \text{ M}\Omega$, indicating the sweat generation with increased body temperature. The decrease in impedance can be attributed to the moisture content in the fabric due to increased sweat amount, which affects its electrical properties and is a key factor in the performance of textile-based sweat sensors (Ravichandran et al., 2023).

After 180 s, the impedance of the sensor was found to have decreased by 61.1%. Later, the impedance decreased gradually. After 600 s, the impedance was measured to be $7.8 \text{ k}\Omega$, suggesting the high sweat generation that wets the sensor fabric. Beyond this point, the impedance appeared

almost constant. We further examined the impedance variation for the period 600–1200 s, wherein it was found that the impedance was slowly varying and at the instant of 780 s, the impedance was found to be $2.6 \text{ k}\Omega$ (inset). Afterward, the variation in impedance became very slow. A slight variation in the impedance under different real-time testing trials was found (Figure S4). From trial 1 to trial 2, a 9, 9.21, 8.9, and 9.1% increase in the sensor's impedance was noticed at periods of 1, 180, 600, and 1200 s, respectively. Interestingly, from trial 1 to trial 3, approximately a 4.5% increase in the impedance of the sensor was observed at the above periods.

We also evaluated the variations in phase angle of the textile sensor while exercising as shown in Figure 8c. The phase angle at no exercise condition and the initial stage was -90° , indicating the high capacitive behavior of the sensor. The phase angle was gradually varied and found to be -18.51° after 600 s of exercise, suggesting that the full wetting of the sensor was possibly due to the increased body temperature (40.7°C). Beyond this temperature, the phase angle varied very slowly (inset of Figure 8c). These results exhibit the performance of the proposed sensor under various exercise stages and sweating conditions. They can provide a cost-effective and easily accessible, portable device for the assessment of hydration status. This is especially important for athletes and individuals who engage in physical activity, as excessive sweating can lead to electrolyte imbalances, which may result in dehydration or other health issues. A comparison of the proposed sensors' features with the recent work is tabulated in Table ST2 (supporting information).

4. Conclusion

In this work, we developed a textile-based wearable impedimetric sensor for monitoring saline solution at different concentrations (0.3–0.9%). The high hydrophilicity (water contact angle $\sim 25^\circ$) of selected fabric with permeable microstructures on its surface makes it a highly suitable contender for sweat sensing. The device characterization exhibited that the textile-based sensing structure has a capacitive nature (phase angle $\sim 85^\circ$) in dry conditions. The capacitance of the textile structure was found to be in the range of 81–58 pF in dry conditions. From the volume optimization study, we found 900 μl was the optimum volume of saline solution to completely wet the sensor. The time optimization analysis revealed that approximately 1 h is the optimum duration to completely dry the fabric sensor at a constant temperature of 37°C which is analogous to a healthy human body temperature. A 3.5-fold decrease in the impedance was exhibited from the developed textile sensor with an increase in saline concentration from 0.3 to 0.9% at both lower frequency range $\sim 100\text{ Hz}$ and higher frequency range $\sim 20\text{ kHz}$. The sensitivity of the proposed sensor was found to be $128.6\ \Omega/\text{saline concentration (\%)}$. The textile sensor was also verified for real human sweat by applying it to the headband of a volunteer while exercising. The textile sensor demonstrated a similar device behavior in the laboratory as well as in real-time human sweat testing.

The proposed sensor can be integrated into different applications. It can be seamlessly integrated inside heavy garments, such as thick winter clothing, headbands, smart carpets, gym-padded equipment. It is also suitable for health and rehabilitation environments, including hospital beds and cushions. The ease of wear, without the hassle of sticking the sensor to the body or skin, enhances user comfort and convenience. Additionally, the proposed sensor can be less affected by electrical noise, ensuring more accurate measurements. The construction of the fabric in weft and warp allows for the natural spreading of the sweat, unaffected by gravity. However, the sensor's performance can be affected by environmental humidity or dry weather, which may impact drying time and accuracy. Additionally, the fabric's permeable microstructures may have limitations in certain environments or applications where different material properties are required. These findings indicate the promising potential of our textile-based wearable impedimetric sensor for wearable sweat biomarker sensing and other impedimetric biosensing applications. Future work will focus on addressing the limitations identified and exploring additional applications for enhanced functionality and reliability.

Authors' contributions

H.Z.: methodology, investigation, software, formal analysis, resources; P.K.: writing original draft, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, software, visualization, writing—review and editing; V.J.: conceptualization, methodology, writing—review and editing; G.M.S.: supervision, conceptualization, methodology, project administration, funding acquisition, writing—review and editing.

Disclosure statement

All authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author on request.

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